

Studies in the Synthesis of Xanthone Derivatives. Part-I

Synthesis of Furanoxanthenes

(MRS.) K. P. SANGHVI, R. J. PATOLIA and K. N. TRIVEDI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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2-Methylresorcinol, on thermal condensation with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate in diphenyl ether gave 6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone, which on allylation, Claisen migration, cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal, gave 4, 5'-dimethylfuran(3', 2'-2,3)xanthone (III). (III), was also synthesised from 3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone by similar series of reactions. 5'-Methylfuran(2',3'-3,4)xanthone (V) was synthesised, starting from resorcinol and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and also from 3-hydroxyxanthone. The structures of intermediate dihydrofuranoxanthenes were confirmed by NMR spectra.

THE synthesis of linear or angular type of Furanoxanthenes have been reported by many workers¹⁻⁵. The synthesis of angular furano compounds is simple, while a linear isomer needs a blocking group⁶ like an acetyl or a methyl group in order that the Claisen migration of an allyloxy derivative produces an appropriate intermediate for the synthesis of a linear furano compound. Rajagopal and co-workers⁴ have used this procedure for the synthesis of linear furanoxanthenes.

In general, two approaches have been used for the building up of a furan ring especially for α -methyl furano derivatives. The one based on Scheinmann and Suschitzky's work¹, gives dihydrofurano compounds, which were dehydrogenated by treatment with N-bromosuccinimide in presence of benzoyl peroxide followed by dehydrobromination with pyridine. The second route is an adaptation of the method of Admas and Rindfus⁷ involving addition of bromine to *o*-acetoxy-allyl derivatives followed by cyclisation and dehydrobromination by alcoholic alkali. Rajagopal and co-workers adopted second route for the synthesis of 4, 5'-dimethylfuran(3',2'-2,3)xanthone(III)⁸, while 5'-methylfuran(2',3'-3,4)xanthone(V)⁹ was synthesised by both the methods,

In the present work, *o*-hydroxy-allylxanthenes were converted into dihydrofuranoxanthenes using conc. sulphuric acid, according to Shaikh and Trivedi¹⁰. This method is very convenient and gives quantitative yields of dihydrofuranoxanthenes, which on dehydrogenation with DDQ in benzene or with palladised charcoal in diphenyl ether gave the corresponding α -methylfuranoxanthenes.

Condensation of 2-methylresorcinol with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate in boiling diphenyl ether, according to Desai, Trivedi and Sethna¹¹

gave 6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ia). This on allylation followed by Claisen migration gave 7-allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ic). Cyclisation of (Ic) by trituration with conc. sulphuric acid afforded 5,5'-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,4',5'-hexahydrofuran(2',3'-6,7)xanthone(II).

Dehydrogenation of (II) by palladised charcoal (10%) furnished 4, 5'-dimethylfuran(3', 2'-2, 3)xanthone (III). (III), was also synthesised by carrying out allylation of 3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone⁹ which on Claisen migration gave (VIb). (VIb), was cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid to yield dihydrofuranoxanthone(VII). The structure of (VII) was confirmed by NMR spectrum (CDCl₃): δ 1.65, 3H doublet, J=7Hz, CH₃ group at C⁵-CH₃; 2.47, 3H singlet, -CH₃ group at C₄-CH₃; 2.9-3.7, 2H multiplet, at C⁴-H₂: 5.15, 1H quartet, J=7Hz, at C⁵-H; 7.3-7.8, 3H multiplet, at C⁵-H, C⁶-H and C⁷-H (aromatic); 8.0, 1H singlet, at C₁-H; 8.35, 1H doublet, J=9Hz, at C⁸-H. This on dehydrogenation with DDQ in dry benzene gave (III). The mixed m. p. of the compounds prepared by the above procedures remained undepressed.

Similarly, resorcinol was condensed with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate in diphenyl ether to give 6-hydroxy-1,2,3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (Id)¹². (Id), on allylation followed by Claisen migration gave 5-allyl-6hydroxy-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (If), which on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid afforded 5'-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4, 4', 5'-hexahydrofuran(3',2'-5,6)xanthone (IV), which was dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal to 5'-methylfuran(2', 3'-3,4)xanthone (V). (V), was also synthesised from 3-hydroxyxanthone by carrying out allylation, Claisen migration and cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid, followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal. The structure of (V) was confirmed by NMR spectrum (CDCl₃): δ 2.6, 3H singlet, -CH₃

group at C5'-CH₃; 6.84, 1H singlet, at C4'-H; 7.45-7.8, 4H multiplet, at C₂-H, C5-H, C6-H and C7-H (aromatic); 8.32, 1H doublet, J=9Hz, at C1-H; 8.5, 1H doublet, J=9Hz, at C8-H. The mixed m. p. of the compounds (V), obtained by both the procedures, remained undepressed.

(I)

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| (Ia) R=CH ₃ , | R ₁ =R ₂ =H |
| (Ib) R=CH ₃ , | R ₁ =-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , R ₂ =H |
| (Ic) R=CH ₃ , | R ₁ =H, R ₂ =-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , |
| (Id) R=R ₁ =R ₂ =H | |
| (Ie) R=R ₂ =H, | R ₁ =-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , |
| (If) R=-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , | R ₁ =R ₂ =H |

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

- | | |
|--|--|
| (VIa) R=CH ₃ , | R ₁ =-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , R ₂ =H |
| (VIb) R=CH ₃ , | R ₁ =H, R ₂ =-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , |
| (VIc) R=R ₂ =H, | R ₁ =-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , |
| (VI d) R=-CH ₂ CH=CH ₂ , | R ₁ =R ₂ =H |

(VII)

(VIII)

Experimental

6-Hydroxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, tetrahydroxanthone (Ia) :

A mixture of 2-methylresorcinol (3 g) and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (4 ml) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (10 ml) for 3 hr., with a short

condenser to facilitate the removal of alcohol formed. After cooling, the separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from dimethyl formamide, m.p. 270°. Yield 2g (Found : C, 72.90 ; H, 6.08. C₁₄H₁₄O₈ requires C, 73.05 ; H, 6.08%)

6-Allyloxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone(Ib) :

A mixture of 6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (2g), allylbromide (1g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml) in water bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into water. The separated product was filtered, washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted compound, the product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 110°. Yield 1.5g (Found : C, 75.68 ; H, 6.34. C₁₇H₁₈O₈ requires C, 75.53 ; H, 6.66%).

7-Allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ic) :

6-Allyloxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (2g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (10 ml) for 8 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml) containing pieces of ice, the separated product was filtered and dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was filtered. The filtrate on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid gave the product, which was crystallised from alcohol. M.p. 221°, yield 1.5 g (Found : C, 75.26 ; H, 6.20. C₁₇H₁₈O₈ requires C, 75.53 ; H, 6.66%). IR spectrum : 1625 cm⁻¹ (γ-pyronyl>C=O group) and a broad band at 3500 cm⁻¹ (aromatic-OH group).

5,5'-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4,4',5'-hexahydrofurano(2',3'-6,7) xanthone(II)

7-Allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (1g) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml) in a water bath for 15 minutes. The contents were poured into crushed ice, the separated product

was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 210°, yield 0.8. (Found : C, 75.18 ; H, 6.35. C₁₇H₁₈O₈ requires C, 75.53 ; H, 6.66%). IR spectrum 1635 cm⁻¹ (γ-pyronyl>C=O group).

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{chloroform}}$ 248 nm (log e 4.22), 255 nm (log e 4.24), 304 nm (log e 4.18).

4,5'-Dimethylfurano (3',2'-2,3)xanthone (III) :

A mixture of 5, 5'-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,4',5'-hexahydrofurano (2',3'-6,7)xanthone (0.5 g) palladised charcoal (10%, 0.3 g) and diphenyl ether (5 ml) was refluxed for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and after cooling, petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 242°. Yield 0.25 g. (Found : C, 77.00 ; H, 4.34. $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 77.27 ; H, 4.55%).

IR spectrum 1640 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $>C=O$ group) ; 880 cm^{-1} (furan ring).

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{Methanol}}$ 25 nm (log e 3.90), 290 nm (log e 3.10), 300 nm (log e 3.12), 360 nm (log e 2.84).

3-Allyloxy-4-methylxanthone (VIa) :

A mixture of 3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (2.5 g), allylbromide (2 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (12 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (300 ml) in a water bath for 11 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above. The product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 149° (lit^s, m.p. 144°). Yield 3 g (Found : C, 76.19 ; H, 5.02. $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 76.67 ; H, 5.26%).

2-Allyl-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (VIb) :

3-Allyloxy-4-methylxanthone (2.5 g) in dimethyl-aniline was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 168°. Yield 2.2 g (lit^s, m.p. 165°) (Found : C, 76.47 ; H, 5.56. $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 76.67 ; H, 5.26%). IR spectrum 1635 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $>C=O$ group) and a broad band at 3200 cm^{-1} (aromatic -OH group).

4,5'-Dimethyl-4'-5'-dihydrofurano(3',2'-2,3)xanthone (VII) :

2-Allyl-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (1.5 g) was triturated with sulphuric acid (85%, 9 ml) in a water bath for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above. It crystallised from alcohol and then from benzene-petroleum ether. M.p. 174°. Yield 1 g. (Found : C, 77.13 ; H, 5.14. $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$; requires C, 76.67 ; H, 5.26%).

4,5'-Dimethylfurano (3'2'-2,3)xanthone (III) :

A mixture of 4,5'-dimethyl-4',5'-dihydrofurano (3',2'-2,3) xanthone (0.6 g) and DDQ (0.535 g) was refluxed in sodium dried benzene (30 ml) in a water bath for 6 hr. The separated product was filtered off and the filtrate on evaporation gave solid, which crystallised from acetic acid and also from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 242° (lit^s, m.p. 235°), yield 0.4 g. Mixed m. p. of this compound

remain undepressed by admixture with the sample obtained by above procedure. (Found : C, 77.29 ; H, 4.4. $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 77.27 ; H, 4.55%).

6-Hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (Id) :

A mixture of resorcinol (3 g) and ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (4 ml) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (10 ml) for 3 hr. with a short condenser to facilitate the removal of alcohol formed. After cooling, the separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from alcohol. M.P. 278°, yield 2.0 g. (Found : C, 72.38 ; H, 5.79. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 72.21, H, 5.55%).

6-Allyloxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ie) :

A mixture of 6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (2 g.), allylbromide (1 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml) in a water bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above, the product crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 88°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 74.98 ; H, 6.24. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 6.25%).

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (If) :

6-Allyloxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (2 g) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 236°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 74.54 ; H, 6.47. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 6.25%).

5'-Methyl-1,2,3,4,4',5'-hexanhydrofurano (3',2',5,6) xanthone (IV) :

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (1 g) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml) in a water bath for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was worked up as described earlier. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 180°, yield 0.8g. (Found : C, 75.23 ; H, 6.40. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 75.00 ; H, 6.25%). IR spectrum : 1635 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $>C=O$ group). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{Methanol}}$ 248 nm (log e. 4.32), 255 nm (log e 4.35), 302 nm (log e 4.12).

5'-Methylfurano (2',3'-3,4)xanthone (V) :

A mixture of 5'-methyl-1,2,3,4,4',5'-hexanhydrofurano (3',2'-5,6) xanthone (0.5 g), palladised charcoal (10%,0.3 g) and diphenyl ether (4 ml) was refluxed for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described before. The product chromatographed on alumina. Elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) gave 5'-methylfurano (2',3'-3,4)-xanthone (V) crystallised from alcohol and also from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 172° (lit^s, m.p. 170°), yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 76.81 ; H,3.95. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8$ requires C,76.80 ; H, 4.00%). IR spectrum : 1645 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $C=O$ group), 825 cm^{-1} (furan ring).

3-Allyloxyxanthone (VIc) :

A mixture of 3-hydroxyxanthone (2 g), allyl-bromide (1.6 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml.) in a water bath for 14 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above. The product crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 136° (lit⁹, m.p. 137°), yield 2.4 g. (Found : C, 75.69 ; H, 4.53. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ requires C, 76.19 ; H, 4.76%).

4-Allyl-3-hydroxyxanthone (VIId) :

3-Allyloxyxanthone (2 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (10 ml) for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described before. The product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 240° (lit⁹, m.p. 253°), yield 1.8 g. (Found : C, 75.78 ; H, 4.76. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ requires C, 76.19 ; H, 4.76%). IR spectrum : 1632 cm⁻¹ (ν -pyronyl>C=O group) and a broad band at 3150 cm⁻¹ (aromatic -OH group).

4',5'-Dihydro-5'-methylfurano(2',3'-3,4)xanthone (VIII) :

4-Allyl-3-hydroxyxanthone (1 g) was triturated with sulphuric acid (85%, 6 ml) in a water bath for 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was worked up as described above. It crystallised from alcohol and benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 181° (lit⁹, m.p. 180°), yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 76.40 ; H, 4.66. C₁₆H₁₂O₃ requires C, 76.19 ; H, 4.76%). NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.54 (3H, d, J=7Hz, C5'-CH₃), 2.80-3.62 (2H, m, C₄'-H₂), 5.15 (1H, q, J=7Hz, C5'-H), 6.7 (1H, d, J=9Hz, C₂-H), 7.2-7.7 (3H, m, C₆-H, C₈-H and C₇-H), 8.06 (1H, d, J=9Hz, C₁-H), 8.25 (1H, d, J=9Hz, C₈-H).

5'-Methylfurano(2',3'-3,4)xanthone (V) :

A mixture of 4',5'-dihydro-5'-methylfurano(2',3'-3,4)xanthone (0.5 g), palladised charcoal (10%, 0.3 g) and diphenyl ether (4 ml) was refluxed for 12 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described before. The product chromatographed on alumina. Elution with benzene-petroleum ether (3 : 7) gave the product, which crystallised from

alcohol, m.p. 172° (lit⁹, m.p. 170°), yield 0.3 g. Mixed m.p. with the compound obtained as above was not depressed. (Found : C, 76.37 ; H, 3.87. C₁₆H₁₀O₃ requires C, 76.81 ; H, 4.00%).

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